

**PRÍPRAVA, CHARAKTERIZÁCIA A OXIDAČNÉ SPRÁVANIE KERAMICKÝCH
POVLAKOV PRIPRAVENÝCH Z ORGANOKREMIČITÝCH PREKURZOROV
S PASÍVNymi PLNIVAMI**

**PREPARATION, CHARACTERIZATION AND OXIDATION BEHAVIOR OF
POLYMER DERIVED CERAMIC COATINGS WITH PASSIVE FILLERS**

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ABSTRACT

The work is aimed at the development of an oxidation/corrosion resistant environmental barrier coating system on steel substrates. After stabilizing the coating slurries, double layers consisting of a bond coat applied by dip coating and a top coat with passive fillers deposited by spray coating were prepared on stainless steel substrates. After thermal treatment in air at 800 °C, uniform and crack-free composite coatings on stainless steel with a thickness up to 90 µm were prepared. The high temperature oxidation behavior of coated and uncoated samples in atmosphere of synthetic air was investigated at the temperatures up to 1000 °C. The tested layers provide effective protection from oxidation at 900 °C and 950 °C, while no significant corrosion damage was observed.

Keywords: polymer-derived ceramics, passive filler, high-temperature oxidation

INTRODUCTION

Recently polymer derived ceramics (PDC) have gained attention as promising candidates for preparation of an environmental barrier coatings (EBC). Advantages of preceramic polymers are based on the use of cost efficient manufacturing routes from polymer processing technologies such as dip-coating or spray coating, low conversion temperatures in a desired atmosphere, tailoring of the microstructure and resulting properties as a function of composition and thermal treatment parameters [1]. The major disadvantage of the used precursor, however, is a shrinkage of more than 50 vol. % occurring during transformation from polymer to an amorphous ceramic. To overcome this drawback passive fillers are applied to control the shrinkage and the porosity of the pyrolyzed ceramics by utilizing different filler combinations [2, 3]. Moreover, the addition of glasses has shown to be a suitable approach to obtain thick and dense coatings. The glass fillers should be responsible for densification and sealing of the system, increasing the efficiency as EBC [4]. In this work, a novel EBC system for steel consisting of a perhydropolysilazane (PHPS) bond coat and a polysilazane-based glass/ceramic composite top coat has been developed. The processing route, microstructure and high-temperature oxidation behavior of the coating are presented.

EXPERIMENTAL

The preparation of the coatings consists of the two main steps: the synthesis of the powder filler AYZ20 ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZrO}_2$) via Pechini sol-gel route and the processing of the coatings. The composition of the AYZ20 filler is derived from $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ eutectic (76,8 mol. % Al_2O_3 , 23,2 mol. % Y_2O_3) and modified by the addition of 20 mol. % ZrO_2 . The PDC system consists of two layers that were consecutively applied to stainless steel (AISI 441) substrates. The bond-coat was prepared from pre-ceramic polymer PHPS by dip-coating of the ultrasonically cleaned metal sheets. The pyrolysis of the bond-coat was performed in air at the temperature of 500 °C for 1 h. The top-coat was prepared from the ceramic matrix forming polysilazane HTT 1800, filled with YSZ (yttria-stabilized zirconia) and AYZ20 powder as passive fillers, and the commercial barium silicate glass particles (G018-311, G018-385, Scott AG) as sealing agents. The resulting mixture was applied onto bond-coat by spray coating technique and the curing of the composite coatings was performed in air at the temperature of 800 °C with a holding time of 1 h. The composition of the top-coat is listed in Tab 1.

Tab. 1: The composition of the composite coating after pyrolysis

YSZ (vol. %.)	AYZ20 (vol. %.)	G018-385 (vol. %.)	G018-311 (vol. %.)	HTT 1800 (vol. %.)
30	21	16	14	19

High temperature oxidation tests were carried out in a high temperature horizontal electric tube furnace (Clasic 0213T, Clasic, Praha, Czech Republic) at the temperatures of 900 °C, 950 °C and 1000 °C and the exposure times in the range of 1 – 48 hours in flowing atmosphere of synthetic air (purity 99.5%, Linde, Slovakia). The SEM/EDS examination of the coatings before and after oxidation tests was conducted with the use of a FEG SEM JEOL

7600f. X-ray powder diffraction analysis (CuK α , 2 θ range 10-80°, Empyrean DY1098, PANalytical B.V., Netherlands) was used to investigate the phase composition of the coatings.

RESULTS

In a Fig. 1a, a SEM micrograph of a HTT 1800/glass composite coating after pyrolysis in air is presented. Micrograph of the cross-section shows that the softening of glass additives leads to the formation of a homogeneous glass/ceramic matrix with evenly distributed filler particles. After thermal treatment in air at 800 °C, uniform, well adherent and crack-free composite coating on stainless steel were prepared. It can be concluded that the addition of powder filler AYZ20 was effective at preventing the formation of cracks and pores. The addition of the filler enable the formation of a rigid skeletal structure in the coating thus facilitating escape of gases during the pyrolytic conversion of the organosilicon precursor. XRD pattern of the coating is displayed in the Fig. 2. After pyrolysis in air the polysilazane-based coating contains three crystalline phases, namely monoclinic and tetragonal ZrO₂, and yttrium aluminum garnet, originating from the powder filler AYZ20.

Fig. 1: Cross-sectional SEM image of the coating after pyrolysis in air at 800 °C

Fig. 2: X-Ray diffraction pattern of the coating after pyrolysis in air at 800°C

Fig. 3a shows the weight gains of the uncoated steel samples as a function of time during high-temperature oxidation. Uncoated steel substrates are subjected to significant oxidation due to the surface oxide scale growth. X-Ray diffraction along with SEM/EDS analysis (not shown) confirmed extensive corrosion of the uncoated steel accompanied by formation of oxide layer comprised Cr₂O₃ sub-layer and Mn-Cr spinel crystals top layer. On the contrary, Fig. 3b distinctly shows that the PDC coating system is able to efficiently reduce the weight gain due to oxidation at elevated temperatures. Compared to uncoated samples, only negligible mass loss was observed at all oxidation temperature. This can be associated with the release of residual hydrogen from cleavage of Si-H and C-H bonds [6]. Prior to long-term oxidation tests, coating systems were pyrolyzed for only 1 h, and this may not necessarily lead to fully transformed and stable ceramic products. However, at the temperature of 1000

°C and after 12 hours of oxidation, a significant weight loss was observed due to the gradual peeling off the protective layer.

Fig. 3: Weight gain at various temperatures and different holding times: a) steel substrate, b) coated steel

From the weight gain measurements it is obvious that the tested layers provide effective protection from oxidation of stainless steel at 900 °C and 950 °C. No significant corrosion damage was observed by SEM analysis (Fig. 4a, b), coating appeared to be well adherent at these temperatures.

Fig. 4: SEM cross-sections of the coating after oxidation tests: a) 900°C/48h, b) 950°C/48h

Moreover, the cracks present on the surface of as-prepared coatings gradually healed due to the softening of the used glass additives. The surface of oxidized specimens was analyzed by XRD to identify new phases formed during oxidation. After longer period of oxidation, crystallization of the glass fillers lead to the formation of new crystalline phases ($\text{Ba}(\text{AlSiO}_4)_2$ – celsian, hexacelsian), but also to the formation of other phases (ZrSiO_4 , $\text{YZr}_8\text{O}_{14}$) as a consequence of chemical reactions between the layer components. At higher oxidation temperature (1000 °C) and after 24 h of oxidation, the presence of oxidation products (MnCrO_4 , Cr_2O_3) in XRD patterns (Fig. 5) was observed.

Fig. 5: XRD patterns of the coating after oxidation tests at 1000 °C

CONCLUSION

A novel polymer-derived ceramic coating system as an environmental barrier coating for stainless steel was developed, using a tailored combination of pre-ceramic precursor with passive fillers and glass frits used as sealants. The protective effect of the PDC coating system in oxidative atmosphere was observed at the temperatures up to 950 °C, while uncoated samples were strongly oxidized.

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